

1 Strategic Factors to Design the Next Generation of Molecular Water Oxidation Catalysts: Lesson 2 Learned from Ruthenium Complexes

3 Abolfazl Ghaderian,¹ Samrana Kazim,^{1,3} Mohammad Khaja Nazeeruddin,² and Shahzada Ahmad^{1,3*}

4 ¹BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures, Bld. Martina Casiano,
5 UPV/EHU Science Park, Barrio Sarriena s/n, 48940 Leioa, Spain Tel: +34 946128811

6 Email:shahzada.ahmad@bcmaterials.net

7 ²Group for Molecular Engineering of Functional Materials, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
8 (EPFL), CH-1951 Sion, Switzerland

9 ³IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, 48009, Spain

11 Abstract

12 Sustainable energy is essential to counter global warming and demands an urgent solution through a
13 multidisciplinary approach. The temperature change stems from the emission of greenhouse gases largely
14 contributed by burning fossil fuels; thus, its replacement with a clean, cheap, and sustainable energy
15 source is paramount. Water is one of the integral sources and is potentially attractive to produce hydrogen
16 (H₂) gas to substitute fossil fuels. In this respect, molecular ruthenium complexes are by far the best
17 molecular water oxidation catalysts (WOCs) to produce proton (H⁺) as a source for H₂ gas production
18 and molecular oxygen (O₂) as a clean by-product. Here, we have made an insightful chronology of the
19 ruthenium-based water oxidation catalysts (RWOCs) and quantify and classified the activation and
20 deactivation pathways in chemical and electrochemical water oxidation reactions (WORs). In this
21 insightful chronology, RWOCs are classified into three main groups, including Ru(N)₆, Ru(N)₅(O), and
22 Ru(N)₄(O)₂ which the last group is the most robust and powerful WOCs. However, still, there is ~200
23 mV overpotential for the Ru(N)₄(O)₂ group of complexes which is one of the current challenges in WOR.
24 Based on the experimental data collected over the last four decades and extracted from these three
25 categories, we suggest a new family of RWOCs that can be the workhorse of RWOCs with very low
26 overpotential. Moreover, the lesson learned from RWOCs has been applied to redesign metal-based
27 WOCs. Such insights provide unparalleled and practical information to produce the WOCs with various
28 metals with high activity and durability that can be employed to cap global warming.

1	Table of Contents
2	1. Introduction
3	2. Evolution of Ru(N) ₆ WOCs
4	3. Evolution of Ru(N) ₅ (O) WOCs
5	4. Evolution of Ru(N) ₄ (O) ₂ WOCs
6	5- Apply lesson learned from RWOCs to the other WOCs
7	6. Conclusion and Perspective for designing next Generation of RWOCs (Ru(N) ₄ (O) ₃)
8	Declaration of Competing Interest
9	Acknowledgement
10	References

11

12 1. Introduction

13 Our planet's appetite for an economical source of energy such as fossil fuels ascends global warming that
14 triggers devastating environmental impacts and health problems. The search for an alternative source of
15 energy is indispensable. A clean, cost-effective, and sustainable source of energy will not only allow
16 addressing the energy crisis but also will avoid the undesired global warming phenomenon and its
17 contamination consequences.[1] Several approaches were put forward during the last decades to combat
18 global warming.[2-17] Among them, artificial photosynthesis inspired by natural photosynthesis is one
19 of the promising approaches.[18-28] In natural photosynthesis, water has been used for billions of years
20 by plants, algae, and cyanobacteria as an abundant source to produces valuable products from CO₂ and
21 release molecular oxygen to the atmosphere (eq 1).[29, 30] Photosynthesis in plants and algae arises in
22 the chloroplast (Figure 1). In this process, firstly light is harvested by pigments located in photosystem II
23 (PhII) generating an electron-hole pair. The electron is anion Pheo⁻ (which is made by pheophytin) and
24 the hole is a radical cation P680⁺.[31] The radical cation acts as oxidizing species, with an oxidation
25 potential of + 1.2 to + 1.3 V, triggering a water oxidation reaction in the oxygen-evolving center (OEC)
26 of PhII. High atomic resolution of the natural molecular structures is an essential step toward the rational

1 design of efficient molecular water oxidation catalysts (WOCs).[31, 32] The map of electron density
 2 manifested Mn_4CaO_5 cluster is responsible for distributing the four oxidizing equivalents on five metal
 3 centers to stabilize the WOC intermediate (Figure 1).[33-36] The electron (e^-) generated by water
 4 oxidation reaction (WOR) is transferred to photosystem I (PhI) by cytochrome b_6f complex. Moreover,
 5 Cytochrome b_6f pumps proton (H^+) into the thylakoid that use to synthesize ATP with the help of ATP
 6 synthase. The transferred electrons are used to reduce NADP^+ to NADPH. Finally, in the Calvin cycle
 7 ATP and NADPH use to convert CO_2 to sugar (Figure 1).[37]

Figure 1. a) Natural photosynthesis process in the chloroplast, and b) the catalytic center of Ph II, $\text{CaMn}_4\text{O}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$.

8
 9 It was accepted, that for designing an artificial molecular water oxidation catalyst, at least two metal
 10 centers must exist in the catalyst structure to remove 4H^+ and $4e^-$ from two water molecules and release
 11 O_2 (eq 2). Thus, it took many years to discover the first water oxidation catalyst in 1982 with the formula
 12 $\text{cis,cis}-[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{OH}_2)\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}-\text{O}-\text{Ru}(\text{OH}_2)(\text{bpy})_2]^{4+}$ (**1** in Figure 2, where bpy stands for bipyridine) after the
 13 discovery of other water oxidation fields.[38, 39] The aforementioned complex (**1**) is called blue dimer
 14 and its activity in water oxidation uncovers several features over the years.[38, 40, 41] The inhibition
 15 factor to stop the catalytic activity of **1** is anion coordination. After adding $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_6$ (Ce^{IV}) as a
 16 chemical oxidant to an acidic solution of the blue dimer and occurring first water oxidation cycle as a
 17 consequence, there is a competition for capturing the catalyst in the low oxidation state either by NO_3^-

1 from acidic solution or water. The former is termed as $[(bpy)_2(H_2O)Ru^{III}-O-Ru^{IV}(ONO_2)(bpy)_2]^{3+}$ is an
 2 inactivate complex and while the latter recovers the catalyst (Figure 2).[42]

3 The blue dimer was a quantum leap and this was followed by the synthesis of a large number of binuclear
 4 Ru complexes.[43] In 2004, to fix the movement along the Ru-O-Ru bridge and improve the interaction
 5 between two Ru=O units, an equatorial ligand called Hbpb⁻ (where Hbbp stands for 2,2'-(1H-pyrazole-
 6 3,5-diyl)dipyridine) was introduced. In $[Ru_2^{II}(\mu-OAc)(bpb)(tpy)_2]^{2+}$ (tpy stands for 2,2':6',2''-terpyridine)
 7 (2), two Ru centers have been located near each other in a backbone, which the equatorial ligand is Hbpb
 8 and acetate is bridging ligand. Electrochemical and spectroscopic techniques confirmed that the acetate
 9 bridge will be replaced by an aqua ligand to make $[Ru_2^{II}(bpb)(tpy)_2(OH_2)_2]^{3+}$. The efficiency increased to
 10 approximately 70% and TOF increased 3 times as compared with the blue dimer under similar conditions.
 11 This increase has been attributed to the reduction in reductive cleavage of the Ru-O-Ru bridge, which
 12 competes with anion coordination side reaction in the blue dimer. It was suggested that the ligand
 13 oxidation roots from the intermolecular reaction are responsible for the deactivation of catalysts. Llobet
 14 *et al.* suggested that by the *in, in* the configuration of oxo, the intermolecular interaction of oxo-oxo is
 15 significant. As a consequence, an intermolecular pathway can trigger O₂. [44]

16
 17 Figure 2. Proposed activation and deactivation pathway for the blue dimer (1) after adding Ce^{IV} as an oxidant. In
 18 accordance with the ref.[42]

19
 20
 21

2. Evolution of Ru(N)₆ WOCs

1 To ratify the presence of two close Ru centers necessary for water oxidation, a mononuclear complex (**4**)
2 (Scheme 1) was prepared to mimic the half of the dinuclear complex (**3**) which is active for water
3 oxidation in 2005. Surprisingly, **4** showed water oxidation activity with turnover numbers (TONs) 260,
4 35, and 20 for different axial ligands with -CH₃,-CF₃- and NH₂ groups in the *para* positions of pyridines
5 respectively. This was one of the most important breakthroughs in this field, as it helped the researchers
6 to design catalyst structures effectively with atom economy.[45]

7 The water oxidation activity of the mononuclear complex was unknown because it was long believed that
8 for evolving oxygen the presence of two Ru–OH₂ groups in a complex was necessary. However, in 2008,
9 a comprehensive mechanistic study was performed on mononuclear complexes by Meyer *et al.* and the
10 result established a water nucleophilic attack (WNA) mechanism for such complexes, which we will
11 discuss in the relevant section.[46] After the introduction of mononuclear water oxidation catalysts,
12 Thummel *et al.* prepared a series of neutral equatorial multidentate ligands derived from 1,10-
13 phenanthroline to follow two goals.[47] First, to inhibit conformational mobility occurring in previously
14 reported complexes with the general formula [Ru(bpy)₂(L)₂] (where L is axial ligand).[48] Secondly, to
15 show that the nitrogen atom from 1,10-phenanthroline can act as an internal base for removing a proton
16 from coordinated water in Ru center similar to **4a** (Scheme 1). Interestingly, it was observed that instead
17 of H₂O coordination, the peripheral sites (nitrogen atoms) of 1,10 phenanthroline coordinated with the
18 metal center (**5**, Scheme 1).

1

2 Scheme 1. Evolution of Ru-N₆ WOC from di-nuclear Ruthenium molecular catalysts.

3

4 The distal ligand on 1,10-phenantroline was changed from 6-membered pyridine ring to 5-membered
 5 imidazole ring in positions 1,9 of the phenantroline to make this bond less favorable; however, ¹H-NMR
 6 and crystal structure showed that there is also coordination between *N*-methyl imidazole and Ru center
 7 instead of H₂O coordination (**6**, Scheme 1). These data pave the way for researchers and it was the starting
 8 point to introduce a family of complexes, here we termed it as [Ru(N)₆]²⁺ where four nitrogen atoms are
 9 from quaterdentate ligand and two nitrogens are from axial ligands. Comparing the TONs of complexes
 10 **5a**, **5b**, and **6** under chemically induced catalysis with Ce^{IV} did not show much difference (TONs are 146,
 11 213, and 281 for **5a**, **5b**, and **6** respectively during 48 hours).[47]

12 By introducing electron-withdrawing groups (EWGs) and electron-donating groups (EDGs) in positions
 13 1,9 of a tetradentate equatorial dpp-type ligand (dpp = 2,9-di-(pyrid-20-yl)-1,10-phenanthroline) (**7**), the
 14 rate of O₂ evolving was investigated and compared with **6**. Interestingly, just **6** showed high catalytic
 15 activity without induction time. Complexes **7 a-d** and **8** showed the induction time between 1-20 minutes.

1 It is noteworthy to mention that the highest activity of **6** is owing to the improved electron-donating
 2 abilities of the imidazole group compared to pyridine which helps the complex to reach high oxidation
 3 states easier. On the other hand, **6** has a higher N-Ru-N angle that can promote water molecule entrance.
 4 Thus, not only the electronic but also structural factors play an important role in water oxidation (Figure
 5 3).

6
 7 Figure 3. Thermal ellipsoid plot representation of the planer fragments of **7a** (left), **6** (middle), and **8**. Color code:
 8 Ruthenium (magenta), nitrogen (blue), carbon (dark gray) and hydrogen (light gray). Reprinted from Ref. [49] with
 9 permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry. Copyright {2015} Royal Society of Chemistry.

10

11 The activity difference between **7b** and **7d** roots from the protonation of $-NMe_2$ in the acidic solution can
 12 change the ligand from electron-donating to electron acceptor. This behavior can also be observed when
 13 the $-NH_2$ group is located in axial positions.[45] The initial TOF of different complexes is compared in
 14 Table 1.

15 Table 1. Kinetic data for water oxidation catalyst **6**, **7b**, **7c**, **7d** and **8**. Reprinted from Ref. [49] with permission
 16 from the Royal Society of Chemistry. Copyright {2015} Royal Society of Chemistry.

Complexes	6	7b	7c	7d	8
$K_{obs}/initial\ TOF^a\ (h^{-1})$	69.2	43.2	16.5	18.5	57.3

17 the $K_{obs}/initial\ TOFs$ were calculated from the slops of manometry measurements

18

19 The role of axial ligands on the electronic properties of the complexes with the general formula
 20 $[Ru(dpp)(4-x-py)_2](PF_6)_2$ was investigated by Zong and Thummel. For this goal, they chose $-NMe_2$ and $-$
 21 CH_3 as EDGs and $-CF_3$ as EWGs on the *para* positions of axial ligands (L) of **7** in Scheme 1. The complex
 22 with $-CH_3$ groups showed the highest activity because of facilitating electron transfer during oxidation
 23 of Ru center. On the other hand, the low activity of the derivative with $-NMe_2$ groups is because of the

1 protonation of the N in acidic pH, as earlier mentioned. In other words, these axial ligands have a strong
 2 electronic effect on changing the metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) bands.[50]
 3 Mechanistic studies using **4a** (Scheme 1), which is the first mononuclear molecular RWOC before
 4 introducing $[\text{Ru}(\text{N})_6]^{2+}$ family, showed a linear relationship between catalyst concentration and rate of
 5 water oxidation, rejecting any dimerization mechanism. To decipher these observations, in 2008,
 6 Thummel *et al.* designed a similar catalyst by putting t-butyl in 7'-positions of the 1,8-naphthyridine rings
 7 of the equatorial ligand to stop any interaction between two catalysts by strict hindrance (**4b**). Expectedly,
 8 the new structure showed the same activity as **4a** and it confirmed that the reaction order in the catalyst
 9 is one. However, Pushkar *et al.* by spectroscopic techniques confirmed that there is two consecutive
 10 oxygen atom transfer from high valent Ruthenium oxo species to non-coordinating nitrogen in an
 11 equatorial position of Ru complex to generate real active species (Figure 4).[51]

12
 13 Figure 4. Proposed catalyst evolution in water oxidation conditions for **4a**. In accordance with the ref. [51]
 14

15 In 2014, several experiments were performed on **8** to elucidate reaction mechanisms related to $[\text{Ru}(\text{N})_6]^{2+}$
 16 family. ^1H NMR and UV-vis experiment confirmed that there is no possibility of replacing of N(pyridyl)
 17 group with water while it is in a low oxidation state. Moreover, mass spectra showed after adding 4 eq
 18 Ce^{IV} ; there is an extra oxygen atom in a complex structure, which as suggested it is coordinated to Ru
 19 center. Moreover, the manometry experiment showed a linear dependence of the rate vs. catalyst

1 concentration. The computational study was performed and confirmed a 7-coordinated structure for both
 2 $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}]^{3+}$ is favored. By combing experimental and computational results, Thummel *et*
 3 *al.* suggested that after oxidation of Ru^{II} to Ru^{III} one aqua complex will coordinate with Ru center and
 4 $2\text{H}^+/1\text{e}^-$ transfer takes place, which creates the seven coordinated $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}]^{2+}$ intermediate. In the next
 5 step, by one-electron oxidation of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}]^{2+}$ and attacking one water molecule to $[\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}]^{3+}$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}\text{-}$
 6 $\text{OOH}]^{2+}$ generates.[45] Based on their DFT calculation, this step demands 1.96 V at pH 0 which is high.
 7 They attributed this slowest kinetic step to the induction of time during oxygen-evolving at pH1.
 8 However, this complex suggested induction time before oxygen evolution specifies an ongoing activation
 9 process. A recent study showed that the electrochemical oxidation of **9**, which has a similar structure to
 10 **8**, triggers axial ligand de-coordination and aqua coordination before catalysis.[52] It is notable to mention
 11 that replacing a nitrogen atom in ligand backbone with a negative charge atom, such as an oxygen atom
 12 in the molecular structure of Ru complexes decreases the redox waves of the complex around 200 mV,
 13 which is a perfect sign to follow these types of transformation reaction. It can be deduced from differential
 14 pulse voltammetry (DPV) (Figure 5a) that the replacement of axial picoline with water at the first
 15 coordination sphere resulted in the redox waves dropped 270 mV (from 1100 to 830 mV) and the
 16 overpotential decreased 160 mV (from 1400 to 1240 mV). The result suggests pathways to produce
 17 catalysts with low overpotentials. For water splitting applications, efficient and durable catalysts with low
 18 overpotential are paramount. [53] At acidic pH, the active species show foot of catalysis at 1.44V.

19
 20 Figure 5. a) DPV of **9** before (red) and after applying a potential of 1.45 V in a pH7 solution and b) 25 consecutive
 21 CVs scan after applying a potential 1.65 V in a solution of **10** at pH 1. Black arrows show the scan direction. Fig.
 22 5b Reprinted from Ref. [52] with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry. Copyright {2020} Royal
 23 Society of Chemistry.

1

2 As we mentioned earlier, all of $[\text{Ru}(\text{N})_6]^{2+}$ types of complexes showed induction time before evolving
3 oxygen. Muckerman *et al.* suggested that the formation of a high oxidation state of these types of complex
4 such as $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{OOH})]^{3+}$ demands time.[54] Nevertheless, there are two cases, which were investigated
5 with experimental details to show what the real active species are in the case of $[\text{Ru}(\text{N})_6]$ family of
6 complexes; (i) $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{pbp})(\text{pic})_2]^{2+}$ (where pbp is 2,2'-(1,10-phenanthroline-2,9-diyl)bis(pyridine))[54]
7 (**7a**) and (ii) $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{qpy})(\text{pic})_2]^{2+}$ (where qpy is 2,2':6',2'':6'',2''':6''',2''''-quaterpyridine) (**10**).[55] These
8 complexes in the presence of an chemical oxidant, undergo ligand oxidation at the two external pyridyl
9 groups forming the corresponding $\text{N}_2\text{-O}_2$ quatrodentate ligand ((i) 2,2'-(1,10-phenanthroline-2,9-
10 diyl)bis(pyridine 1-oxide) (pbp- O_2) and (ii) [2,2':6',2'':6'',2''':6''',2''''-quaterpyridine] 1,1''-dioxide (qpy- O_2))
11 (Figure 6). In line with complex **9**, the redox wave of new active species showed a 440 mV decrease in
12 redox potential as compared with deactivate complex and ~ 230 mV decrease in overpotential. By
13 considering around a 200 mV decrease in the redox wave for every negative charge, this point perfectly
14 fits two negative charges that coordinated to the metal center after the convention to active species.
15 Moreover, the O1-Ru1-O_2 bite angle for entering water is 101.86° that is 19.03° less than the deactivate
16 complex. The new $[\text{Ru}(\text{N})_4(\text{O})_2]$ complexes generated in this manner are water oxidation catalysts.

17

18

19 Figure 6. a) ORTEP plot of **9** after electrochemical oxidation and (b) **10** after chemical activation respectively at
20 pH1. Thermal ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability. H atoms have been omitted for clarity.[52, 55] Fig. 6a
21 reprinted from Ref. [52] with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry. Copyright {2020} Royal Society
22 of Chemistry, and Fig. 6b reprinted with permission from ref. [55], copyright {2014} John Wiley and Sons.

23 In the case of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{N})_6]^{2+}$ family of complexes, where the equatorial ligands are flexible, the main
24 pathways taking place with chemical water oxidation are depicted in Figure 7 and involve Ru-N O-atom

1 insertion for two external pyridyl groups. This reactivity toward oxidation can be mainly associated with
2 the low energy barrier for the C-C bond rotation of the external pyridyl groups of tetradentate flexible
3 ligands. However, in the rigid structures, in which the equatorial pyridines cannot rotate, electrochemical
4 oxidation showed axial ligand decooordination.[52]

5
6 Figure 7. N₄ tetradentate equatorial ligands. The arrows show the C-C bond rotational axis.

7

8 3. Evolution of Ru(N)₅(O) WOCs

9 With the seminal work in 2005 and the introduction of the mononuclear water oxidation catalyst,[45] in late
10 2008, a new family of Ru complexes was introduced having a general formula [Ru(N)₅(O)]²⁺ (where N₅
11 includes terpyridine type of ligands (N₃) and bipyridine type of ligands (N₂), and O is a monodentate ligand
12 (being H₂O in all cases after dissolving in aqueous solution)).[46, 56] The first molecules of these families
13 called [Ru(tpy)(bpm)(OH₂)]²⁺ (**11a**) (bpm stands for 2,2'-bipyrimidine) and [Ru(tpy)(bpz)(OH₂)]²⁺ (**11b**) (bpz
14 stands for 2,2'-bipyrazine) were prepared to investigate the mechanism of mononuclear complexes.
15 Spectroscopic techniques confirmed that after using 4 eq. Ce^{IV} as an oxidant, two water molecules consumed
16 and one molecule O₂ will be realized and resulted in introducing a new mechanism called WNA.[46] Figure 8
17 represents a general mechanism for WNA.

Figure 8. Two main mechanistic pathways for water oxidation reaction are called WNA and I2M.

- 1 In this family of complexes, the EWGs such as $-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ on 4,4' positions of bpy show higher TON
- 2 and less rate compared to EDGs (such as $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{OMe}$) (12). The more activity of the EDGs is interpreted
- 3 by lowering the redox potentials of $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}$. As it was expected for more EDGs, the
- 4 MLCT band in UV-vis is redshifted and the first redox potential becomes less positive in line with
- 5 decreasing the energy level of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO).[56]

- 6
- 7 Scheme 2. RWOCs with general formula $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_5(\text{O})$, where here O is H_2O or Cl.

1 An uncommon behavior was observed by replacing one of the pyridines of bpy (**14a**) with 1,8-
2 naphthyridine, called pynap (**13**), the TON increased 3 and 2 order compared with un-substituent complex
3 and -NO₂ substituents in positions 4,4' respectively (**12**).[56] It was reported that the combination of
4 delocalization and electronegativity properties in pynap causes this effect. ¹H-NMR showed that H₆ of
5 pyridine appeared in high ppm because of chloride vicinity in the axial position, which is in line with its
6 crystal structure. Moreover, the activity of **13** was compared with RuO₂, RuCl₃ and Ru(DMSO)₄Cl₂ to
7 understand if **13** decompose to one of these compounds. Only Ru₂O showed activity that was lesser than
8 **13**. Hence, converting the complex in oxidative condition to one of these compounds is rejected. The
9 stability of [Ru(N)₅(O)]²⁺ family was investigated by adding 40 eq Ce^{IV} to the pH1 solution of **14a**, and
10 the catalyst was collected by adding aqueous NH₄PF₆. ¹H-NMR showed broad peaks; however, after
11 adding ascorbic acid as the reducing agent, the peak related to the complex was recovered. The main
12 species in the mass spectrum of recovered catalyst was [Ru(tpy)(bpy)Cl]²⁺. [56]

13 In 2011, Fujita *et al.* investigated complex **15a** and **15b** toward water oxidation. Complex **15a** with a
14 proximal base (nitrogen atom) showed negligible water oxidation activity.[57] The investigation of pH
15 showed that at high pH, complex (**15a**) has higher p*k*_a (11.3) than the other isomers **15b** and **14b** (9.1 and
16 9.7 respectively). It was suggested that hydrogen bonding is responsible for stabilizing Ru complex (**15a**)
17 and preventing water oxidation activity. However, the gas evolution analysis shows the CO₂ peak is much
18 higher than O₂ confirming the presence of decomposition in pynap or/and tpy ligands.

19 The light-assisted conversion of trans-isomer (complex **15b**) to cis isomer (complex **15a**) was reported by
20 Yagi *et al.* Kinetic studies confirmed that stoichiometric photoisomerization reaction to trans isomer is
21 first-order. However, k_{O₂} in the case of cis-isomer decreased one order of magnitude. [58] Furthermore,
22 the DFT calculation was made on both isomers and the result uncovered orbital amplitude on Ruthenyl
23 group of cis isomer is less than the trans one. As a result, in cis isomer, some of this orbital amplitude
24 delocalize on the bynp ligand, and the power O-O bond formation decreases by inferior overlapping
25 between the orbital of unpaired electron of oxygen from incoming water and Ru-O^{IV} group. [59] A similar
26 trans to cis photoisomerization was observed by Tanaka *et al.*[60]

1 In 2012, the electronic properties of bpy ligand were manipulated by substitution of H atoms with F atoms
2 in the positions of 5 and 6 of bpy to investigate its effect on the electronic perturbation of the Ru center.
3 Comparing TOF of aforementioned complexes presents a fall by a factor for 4 and 9 for complex **16a** and
4 **16b** respectively about the un-substituent (**14b**). Compared to the un-substituent complex, **16a** showed a
5 decline in the pK_a by 0.8 log units and **16b** showed a rise in the pK_a by 0.6 log units. The electrochemical
6 investigation was made to quantify that this 1.4 log units increase in the case of **16b**, compared to **16a** is
7 related to the H-bonding effect or not. Cyclic voltammetry showed two F substituent complexes have
8 similar redox properties; however, **16a** and **16b** showed an anodic shift (60 – 70 mV respectively) in
9 comparison with un-substituted (**14b**). From such experiments, it was suggested that since **16a** and **16b**
10 have similar electronic behavior, the hydrogen bonding is responsible for a decrease in the rate of water
11 oxidation reaction which the difference between pK_a of these three complexes confirms this hypothesis.
12 They concluded that this step can be rate-determining.[61]

13 In 2013, the electronic and steric effect on the catalytic activity of $[Ru(N)_5(O)]^{2+}$ type of complex was
14 investigated. The ligand with quinoline moiety next to axial chloride (**17a**) showed higher TON compared
15 with its isomer (**17b**) (TONs, 66 vs 9). In sharp contrast, the complex involving 2,2' biquinoline (**17c**)
16 failed to show any activity for another complex. By replacing the bpy ligand with 1,10-phen (**18a**), the
17 activity and stability have increased compared to bpy (TONs, 450 vs 270 and K_{obs} , 280 vs 190 s^{-1}).
18 However, the substitution of the hydrogen in the ortho positions of 1,10-Phen by $-CH_3$ groups decreases
19 stability for bpy ligand (**18b**, TON 60 and K_{obs} , 50 s^{-1}). Interestingly, Cl⁻ ligated complex with $-CH_3$ in the
20 ortho positions of 1,10-Phen did not show any activity.[62]

21 The effects of EWGs and EDGs on bpy ligand coordinated to Ru center on catalytic activities were
22 investigated by Berlinguette *et al.* (**19**). EWGs increased the stability (TON) of the catalyst by increasing
23 the π -back bonding to bpy ligands; as a consequence, the Ru in its high oxidation state will be less electron
24 deficient. However, EDGs increase the rate (TOF) by making the high oxidation state more stable. The
25 aforementioned effect also was observed by voltammetry that $Ru^{V/IV}$ redox potential of $-OMe$

1 substituents lead to around 100 mV lower potential than –COOH one[63] which is in line with reported
2 data by Llobet *et al.*[61]

3 In 2011, Yagi *et al.* reported that by placing the EDGs on 4'-positions of central pyridine in the tpy ligand
4 (**20**) the TOF increases one order of magnitude compared to unsubstituted one (Table 2). It was reported
5 that the EtO-group decreases the oxidation potential of Ru^{II/III} and Ru^{III/IV} 56 and 22 mV, respectively.
6 However, the TON of the fastest modified catalyst is 690, which is lower than the un-substituted one.
7 Based on the crystal structures, the authors concluded that due to the substituted complex (EtOtpy), the
8 bond distance between the Ru and N atoms increases as compared to the un-substituted one, the oxidation
9 of the ligands is easier, and thus decomposition occurs.[64,65]

10 Table 2. v_{O_2} for [Ru(Rtpy)(bpy)Cl]²⁺ derivatives. Reprinted from Ref. [64] with permission from the Royal Society
11 of Chemistry. Copyright {2011} Royal Society of Chemistry.

Rtpy	v_{O_2} (nmol s ⁻¹)
tpy	0.34
EtOtpy	4.4
MeOtpy	2.4
Metpy	0.61
Cltpy	0.43

Ce^{IV}, 0.5 mmol (0.1 M), [Ru(Rtpy)(bpy)OH₂], 0.1 μmol (20 μM); pH= 1.0; liquid volume, 5.0 ml.

12
13 The power of electron donation of tpy group increases by adding t-butyl groups (the new tpy group is
14 called 4,4',4''-tri-t-butyltpy). **21a** showed enhanced activity in water oxidation compared with **14a**. H
15 atoms were substituted on the *para* positions of pyridines by t-butyl groups on bpy (**21b**) but the TON
16 decreased compared with **14a**. The tpy and bpy were substituted with t-butyl at the same time (**21c**),
17 however; the TON dropped much more than **21b**.

18 Masaoka and Sakai used the H₂O ligated complex as a water oxidation catalyst and the activity of this
19 complex was compared with Cl ligated complex (**14a**). In the case of the H₂O ligated complex, O₂
20 evolving started immediately after the addition of chemical oxidant; however, Cl ligated complex showed
21 induction time, which was observed by other groups. After adding NaCl 0.5 M to the solution of Cl

1 ligated complex solution, no catalytic activity was observed and the authors concluded that Cl^- must be
2 replaced with H_2O to create active species. Equation 3 shows in the presence of Cl^- , the keep equilibrium
3 in the left side (equation 1).[66]

4

5 To elucidate the stability of the catalyst, spectroscopy techniques were employed UV-vis and electrospray
6 ionization Time-of-Flight (ESI-TOF). UV-vis spectra showed, after adding 40 eq. of oxidant to the
7 solution of the complex, which must show 10 catalytic cycles, the band at 476 nm related to Metal to
8 ligand charge transfer (MLCT) disappeared, confirming that Ru^{II} does not exist in the catalytic cycle.
9 Interestingly, by adding an excess amount of ascorbic acid to the oxidized solution of the catalyst, the
10 band at 476 nm recovered (Figure 9).[46]

11

12

13 Figure 9. UV-vis spectra of an aqueous solution of complex **14b**. (b) after adding 40 eq. Ce^{IV} , c) 2hr after addition
14 of Ce^{IV} d) 24hr after addition of Ce^{IV} e) after addition of ascorbic acid as reducing agent to oxidized complex.
15 Reprinted with permission from ref. [66] supporting information. Copyright {2009} Chemical Society of Japan.

16

17 ESI-TOF mass spectrometry was used to investigate the stability of catalysts during the catalysis. The
18 attempt for doing the quantitative experiment had failed because of low accuracy in integrated intensities.
19 However, the spectral features of the sample were similar, before and after water oxidation activity,
20 subsequently, no decomposition after 10 cycles' water oxidation was shown or was negligible.

1 Electrochemical investigation of such complex showed that after two redox waves at 810 mV and 1120
2 mV (vs. SCE), a catalytic current at potentials around 1300 mV vs. SCE appeared that shows around 380
3 mV overpotential at pH1. These electrochemical results confirmed that $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ must oxidize into $\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$
4 to evolve oxygen [66] and it is in line with DFT calculation for producing O_2 by Ce^{IV} for chemical
5 oxidation (Figure 8).[46]

6 Besides Masaoka and Sakai, Berlinguette *et al.* investigated the stability of $[\text{Ru}(\text{N}_5)(\text{L})]^{2+}$ types of
7 complex. Their experimental data, both types of catalysts including $\text{L}=\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Cl coordinated complex,
8 showed induction time before oxygen-evolving, by adding 30 equivalents Ce^{IV} to the solution of catalysts.
9 In the case of the H_2O coordinated complex, the induction time was shorter with a higher initial rate
10 compared with Cl ligated complex.[63] This observation creates the uncovered question that this
11 induction time is because of converting complex to another active complex or is because of converting
12 Ru^{II} to Ru^{IV} . These observations are per the earlier reports.[66] The catalyst was recovered after adding
13 an excess amount of oxidant (1000 eq. Ce^{IV}) to the acidic solution of the catalyst. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and ESI-MS
14 confirmed that tpy was very stable; however, there is a complete conversion of N atoms of bpy to N-O
15 and de-coordination of oxidized bpy ligand consequently. Therefore, the deactivation pathway is related
16 to the de-coordination of oxidized bpy ligand. Interestingly, without Ru catalyst, no oxidation of bpy was
17 observed by stirring bpy in a 1 M acidic solution containing 1000 eq. of oxidant (Figure 10).

18
19 Figure 10. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of bpy (up) and the oxidized form of bpy (down) after adding 1000 equivalents of Ce^{IV} in an
20 acidic solution of **14b**. Reprinted with permission from ref. [63]. Copyright {2010} American Chemical Society.

21

1 In all complexes that were prepared by Berlinguette *et al.*, [63] Cl⁻ ligated catalysts showed a longer
 2 induction time compared with H₂O-ligated catalysts. Spectroscopic techniques such as ¹H-NMR and UV-
 3 vis confirmed that Cl⁻ ligated derivatives convert to H₂O-ligated ones in aqueous media. [63, 67] This
 4 supports the mechanism proposed by the Meyer group and rejected the possibility of a 7-coordinated
 5 intermediate with the presence of Cl⁻. In line with the last result, it was reported that the presence of an
 6 excess amount of Ce^{IV} at pH1 **14b** can slowly and irreversibly convert to an active dinuclear complex by
 7 losing a bpy ligand. The resulting O²⁻ bridged complex *trans*-[(tpy)(bpy)Ru^{IV}(μ-O)Ru^{IV}(tpy)(OH₂)(O)]⁴⁺
 8 (Figure 11b) is a more robust catalyst than the parent complex (Figure 11a). [68]

10
 11 Figure 11. a) **14b** before adding Ce^{IV}, and b) ORTEP plot (ellipsoids drawn at 50% probability) of the X-ray crystal
 12 structure after adding Ce^{IV}. H atoms omitted for clarity. Reprinted with permission from ref. [68]. Copyright {2014}
 13 John Wiley and Sons.

14 Since the induction time was before oxygen evolving in this family of complexes, Pushkar *et al.* proposed
 15 that the active species formed after oxygen atom transfer to the N atom of bpy. Spectroscopic techniques
 16 such as electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) and resonance Raman (rR) suggest that when the metal
 17 at the center reaches a high oxidation state (Ru^{IV}=O), instead of one more electron oxidation, the transfer
 18 of oxygen atom to nitrogen of pyridine occurs (Figure 12). The authors suggested that since dimer
 19 formation cannot be the reason for induction time, a fast N-O formation is responsible for induction time
 20 and creates the active species very fast.

1 Figure 12. The formation of N-O as a reactive intermediate. In accordance with the ref. [69]

2

3 4. Evolution of Ru(N)₄(O)₂ WOCs

4 In a seminal work, Sun *et al.* introduced carboxylate groups with two negative charges (as exist in
5 Mn₄CaO₅ cluster) in equatorial ligand and showed catalytic activity comparable with nature with a low
6 overpotential (~200 mV vs. ~160 mV in OEC in photosystem II).[70] The general formula for this Ru-
7 base complex is [Ru(bda)(L)₂], where bda is 2,2'-bipyridine-6,6'-dicarboxylate (N₂-O₂), and L is axial
8 ligands with 2 picoline ligands (N₂) called Ru-bda. Here, Ru-bda complexes have been considered as the
9 base structure for Ru(N)₄(O)₂ family of WOCs. The seven coordinated valent species were reported for
10 the first time by crystallization after adding excess Ce^{IV} as an oxidant to a pH 1 solution of **22a**.

11 Mechanistic study at pH1 showed the rate of reaction to Ru-bda concentration is order two and the
12 mechanism for oxygen-evolving is as the result of interaction between two Ru^{IV}=O molecules (I2M,
13 Figure 8). The kinetic data confirmed the aforementioned step is the rate-determining step known as O-
14 O bond formation step. The high spin density on O atom with radical properties is one of the necessary
15 conditions for the aforementioned step.[70-72] Furthermore, the computational results showed that the
16 I2M mechanism is preferred at both basic and acidic pHs.[73]

17 The impact of EWG/EDG and hydrophilic/hydrophobic groups on the activity of the complex was
18 investigated. The presence of EWG such as -EtCO₂ (**22b**) and Br (**22c**) on axial pyridine groups showed
19 higher activity and stability. It is suggested that the EWGs make Ru^V=O more unstable and as a
20 consequence, the activity toward O-O the bond formation will increase.

21 On the other hand, the axial pyridines with substituted hydrophobic groups such as -(CH₂)₃Ph (**22d**)
22 showed higher activity than hydrophilic ones such as sulfonate groups. It is proposed that as these
23 complexes follow the I2M mechanism, the higher hydrophobicity in the aqueous solution favors the O-O
24 bond formation.[74]

25 To decrease the kinetic barrier of the dimerization process and induce better interaction between two
26 centers, π -extended axial ligands such as isoquinoline (**23a**) and phthalazine (**23b**) were used.[75-78] By
27 using these two ligands, it was possible to improve the interaction between two catalysts boosting π - π

1 stacking which decrease the energy barrier for the O-O bond formation via radical coupling. In the case
2 of **23a**, after adding 8000 eq Ce^{IV}, the extracted solution of catalyst by CH₂Cl₂ was investigated by MS
3 spectrum and the result showed that isoquinoline de-coordination is the main decomposition pathway.[75]
4 In 2014, –OMe groups were introduced on the isoquinoline axial ligands to favor π - π stacking and
5 increase the activity (**24**). The water oxidation activity under similar conditions for **24**, **23a**, and **25**
6 showed different TOFs of 381, 256, and 2 s⁻¹ respectively. The DFT calculation suggested that the
7 electrostatic interaction between the positive charge of substituted carbon with –OMe on isoquinoline
8 ligand of the Ru-bda complex and the negative charge of the C atom of –OMe group on the isoquinoline
9 ligand of the second Ru-bda complex facilitated staking energy. This result confirmed that π -stacking
10 interaction is the key factor influencing the reactivity of Ru-bda oxidation catalysts (**24**).[79] It is
11 noteworthy to mention that the EDGs just affect the Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} redox potential and there is no relation
12 between first redox potential and catalytic activity. The redox potential Ru^{III/II} for **25** appeared at $E_{1/2}$ =
13 0.78, which showed 80 mV increases compare to **23a**, and the two next oxidation potentials (Ru^{IV/III} and
14 Ru^{V/IV}) occur in lower potentials 20 and 10 mV respectively compared with **23a**. However, under similar
15 conditions, **23a** is much faster than **25**. [79] This phenomenon was observed in the other research
16 works.[76, 80] Besides π -extended axial ligands, the TOF of **22a** confined in the nanocage showed as
17 high as two times that of the homogeneous **22a** thanks to the enhanced interaction for the catalysts
18 following the I2M mechanism in the limited space of nanocages.[81,82]

Scheme 3. Ru(N)₄(O)₂ WOCs and the ones inspired by this family.

1

2

3

4 Bimolecular coupling of Ru-bda complex limits the application in the solution and on the surface of the

5 electrode. In 2015, the covalent grafting was generated between Ru-bda complex and glassy carbon

6 electrode by reduction of diazonium complex. However, the result showed this complex has less catalytic

7 activity compared with the catalyst in homogenous conditions. Furthermore, over time the complex

8 decomposed to RuO₂. [83] Reports dealing with designing the dinuclear complex with a bridging ligand

9 to overcome such limitations without direct drifting to the surface of the electrode were reported. [84, 85]

10 Wurthner *et al.* synthesized a series of cyclic structures with two [86] three Ru-bda centers [87-89] (**26** in

11 Scheme 3). The macrocyclic structure with three Ru-bda centers forced the synthesized Ru-bda to catalyze

12 molecular oxygen evolution by WNA mechanism with an extraordinary TOF, which exceeded 100 s⁻¹.

13 The photo-driven oxidation conditions with [Ru(bpy)₃]Cl₂ as the photosensitizer [90] and Na₂S₂O₈ as the

14 sacrificial electron acceptor showed a TON of 1255 and a TOF of 13.1 s⁻¹ in nM concentration. [87] The

15 modification of the axial and the bda ligands in the Ru macrocyclic did not show any desired tuning of

1 the oxidation potentials of the Ru macrocycles.[91] For practical applications, the immobilization of
 2 homogeneous WOCs onto the conductive surfaces [92] is necessary following by different methods such
 3 as non-covalent π - π interactions between conductive material such as carbon nanotubes [93,94] or direct
 4 covalent bands.[95] **26** was immobilized on multi-walled carbon nanotube electrodes which repetitive
 5 cyclic voltammetry scans showed a catalytic current density of 186 mA cm^{-2} at a potential of 1.45 V and
 6 an onset overpotential of 330 mV.[96] Designing a bulky group on axial ligands which can act as the base
 7 or ligand in the first coordination sphere is another way to block the I2M mechanism and favor WNA.
 8 An asymmetric Ru-bda complex (**27**) was reported which after applying an oxidation potential and
 9 reaching to high oxidation state (**27a**) by coordination of H_2O , an intramolecular oxidation of a benzylic
 10 alcohol by a high valent ruthenium-oxo group (**27b**), leads to an active catalyst (**27c**) for the WOCR(**27d**).
 11 A foot of the wave analysis (FOWA) of the catalytic wave based on the WNA mechanism, accounts for
 12 a $\text{TOF}_{\text{max}} = 0.74 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Figure 13).[97] Generally, methylene groups in the ligand backbone near to catalytic
 13 center are prone to oxidize, such points should be taken into account before designing the robust WOC.
 14 [98,99]

15
 16 Figure 13. Suggested mechanism to generate **27d**^{IV} as active species from **27**. Reproduced with permission from
 17 ref. [97]. Copyright {2020} American Chemical Society.

18
 19 A Ru complex is reported with an equatorial ligand called Ru-pda (where pda is phenanthroline
 20 dicarboxylate, **28** in Scheme 3) which has a similar environment as Ru-bda complexes and more rigidity
 21 and open site for hepta coordination with a TOF of 0.1 s^{-1} . Kinetic studies confirmed that this catalyst
 22 follows a WNA mechanism. DFT calculation suggested that the rigidity of this complex compared with

1 Ru-bda is responsible for its low catalytic performance (Figure 14).[100] Moreover, a DFT study showed
2 the orientation of hydrophobic oxo in Ru-pda is directed toward the more hydrophobic part of another
3 Ru-pda, which disfavors I2M.[101]

4
5 Figure 14. pda and bda equatorial ligands. In accordance with the ref. [100].

6 Several factors that influence the impressive behavior of Ru-bda based complex: (i) carboxylic groups
7 stabilize high oxidation states; (ii) the bda ligand provides the open O-Ru-O angle of 124° for **22** which
8 is 34° larger than an octahedral structure and creates a highway for the coordination of water and allowing
9 the coordination seven (CN7); (iii) flexibility of Ru(bda) helps the complex to adjust its structure in the
10 transition state (iv); DFT calculation suggested that Ru-O' has a high oxyl radical character which follows
11 the I2M mechanism.

12 Ru-bda family of complexes can be oxidized both in solution and in the solid-state under air (atmospheric
13 oxygen). The stability of **21** was investigated in acetonitrile at room temperature under atmospheric
14 oxygen. After one day of stirring, the color of the solution changed from red to green. ESI mass confirmed
15 that there are three compounds including **22**, oxidation of complex **22**, and oxidation of $-\text{CH}_3$ group on
16 axial ligands (**22a**, **22b**, and **22c**) in solution state. Furthermore, they were able to isolate the
17 $[\text{Ru}(\text{bda})(\text{pic})(4\text{-HOOC-py})]$ in solid-state (Figure 15).[102] However, the catalysis deactivation pathway
18 by adding a stoichiometric and excess amount of Ce^{IV} to the pH1 solution of **22** showed a negligible
19 amount of CO_2 which they concluded that oxidative decomposition is not the main route.[75]

20

1

2 Figure 15. The detected species after aerobic oxidation of **22** in solution. Reproduced with permission from ref.
 3 [102]. Copyright {2009} American Chemical Society.

4 A remarkable example is **29** that after adding Ce^{IV} by following a six-electron process, first converts to
 5 **29a** (Figure 16), and later the complex converts to the active species, which is **29b** (Figure 16). The
 6 aforementioned complex eventually converts to **22** and by releasing CO_2 , this result has been confirmed
 7 by ESI mass spectrum.

8

9 Figure 16. Proposed activation pathway for **29** in presence of Ce^{IV} to convert to active species. Reproduced with
 10 permission from ref. [103]. Copyright {2018} John Wiley and Sons.

11 Several research groups are inspired by Ru-bda to produce the catalyst with high stability and activity. In
 12 2015, a new Ru catalyst (**30**, Scheme 3) was reported with the formula $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{OH})(\text{tda}-\kappa\text{-N}^3\text{O})(\text{py})_2]$
 13 (where tda is = [2,2':6',2''-terpyridine]-6,6''-dicarboxylate and py is Pyridine) showed a high turnover
 14 frequency recorded of 7700 s^{-1} at pH 7.0 and 50000 s^{-1} at pH 10.0 in homogenous solution after applying
 15 1.2 V.[104] An increasing number of pyridines in the equatorial ligand of Ru-bda to three provides a
 16 dangling carboxylate group in **30** acting as an internal base, which facilitates removing a proton from
 17 incoming water. The aforementioned process speeds up O–O the bond formation, which is a rate-limiting
 18 step of reaction in the WNA mechanism that is why an impressive catalytic activity is observed. This

1 catalyst has been used in the heterogeneous phase producing the best electro-anodes and photo-anodes
2 for the water oxidation catalysis available.[105-107]

3
4 Figure 17. tda and mcbp equatorial ligands when Ru center is in a high oxidation state. Reprinted with
5 permission from ref. [108]. Copyright {2019} John Wiley and Sons.

6
7 The experimental result shows the activation of **30** is incomplete, which is the main drawback for this
8 complex and decreases the activity when incorporated in hybrid anodes. Hence, Akermark *et al.* designed
9 a new catalyst by replacing two pyridines in tda equatorial ligand with two benzimidazoles which makes
10 a new equatorial ligand called mcbp²⁻ (where mcbp²⁻ is 2,6-bis(1-methyl-4-(carboxylate)benzimidazol-
11 2-yl)pyridine).[108]

12 This change brings one more carbon atom between the coordinated nitrogen and carboxylic groups in the
13 equatorial ligand of the Ru complex. It is stated that this extra carbon atom changes the external five-
14 membered ring to a highly disordered six-membered ring, which in turn makes the Ru-O bonds weaker
15 and facilitates the complete conversion to active species. The experimental result showed that there is a
16 complete conversion to Ru-aqua species with $\text{TOF}_{\text{max}} \approx 40\,000\text{ s}^{-1}$ at pH 9.0 (Figure 17).

17 Arguably, the phosphate group is well known for the water molecule adsorption and it acts as a base to
18 facilitate O-O bond formation by intermolecular H⁺ transfer from incoming water.[109, 110] Concepcion
19 *et al.*[111] and Grotjahn *et al.*[112] in a parallel work presented an innovative idea to replace the
20 carboxylate groups in bda with the phosphates groups to act not only as a ligand to stabilize Ru at a high
21 oxidation state but also as a base near to the catalytic center.[112-114] In 2019 a new Ru complex with
22 the general formula $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{H}_3\text{tPa}-\kappa\text{-N}_3\text{O})(\text{py})_2]^+$ (**31**) (where H₃tPa is deprotonated 2,2':6',2''-

1 terpyridine,6,6''-diphosphonic acid (H₄tPa) and pyridine (py)) was prepared which the carboxylate groups
 2 was replaced with phosphonate groups and showed high electrocatalytic activity after conversion to a
 3 catalyst. In this case, after applying a potential of 1.3 V (vs. NHE) and reaching a high oxidation state
 4 (IV), one hydroxide ligand coordinates Ru center, which triggers O-atom insertion into the *para* position
 5 of CH bond of one of the external pyridine groups of equatorial ligand forming the active species (Figure
 6 18, right). The later complex is an efficient water oxidation catalyst with a TOF of 16000s⁻¹ with a high
 7 overpotential of 530 mV at pH 7, which is less than **30** (605 mV).[115] Although **30** and **31** have a high
 8 N-Ru-O angle for entering the water, the high overpotential in **30** and **31** compared with Ru-bda types of
 9 complexes is because of the difference in electronic properties which in the case of **30** and **31** a less
 10 negative charge coordinated to Ru center.

11
 12 Figure 18. a) X-ray structure ORTEP views (at 50% probability) for **31** and b) after applying a potential of 1.3V,
 13 which converted, to an active species. Color code: Ru, cyan; P, pink; N, blue; O, red; C, black; H, white. Reprinted
 14 with permission from ref. [115]. Copyright {2020} American Chemical Society.

15
 16 Recently, a Ru-based WOC called [Ru(bds)(pic)₂] (**32**) (where bds²⁻ is = 2,2'-bipyridine-6,6'-
 17 disulfonate) containing a tetradentate, dianionic sulfonate ligand at the equatorial position.
 18 Electrochemical water oxidation of **32** in neutral conditions gave a TOF of 12900 s⁻¹ at a scan rate of 1.3
 19 V s⁻¹ while **22a** displayed a TOF of 300 s⁻¹ at the scan rate of 2.0 V s⁻¹. [116] It is worthwhile to mention
 20 that for the calculation of TOF there are two popular methods (1) the ratio of catalytic current (*i*_{cat}) vs. the
 21 noncatalytic Faradaic current (*i*_p) and (2) FOWA. In FOWA, choosing catalytic points is subjective;
 22 hence, the data with the former method is more reliable. Although **30**, **31** need electrochemical activation
 23 before electrochemical measurement; they are currently the fastest electrochemical water oxidation

1 catalysts together with **32**[116] that inherently is active WOC. On the other hand, thanks to the mindful
2 design of the Ru-bda family of complexes, which is inspired by nature, they are the most active and stable
3 chemical WOCs.

4 Scanning the data reported over the last four decades for the three main groups of RWOCs called Ru(N)₆,
5 Ru(N)₅(O) Ru(N)₄(O)₂ (Table 3), guide us toward several interesting information that may be used for all
6 types of WOCs. (i) Negative charge in the first coordination sphere may stabilize the metal center at a
7 high oxidation state and facilitate WOR in low overpotential. (ii) Having a wide bite angle for water
8 coordination is the second important factor that must be taken into account for designing the next
9 generation of WOCs with a high catalytic activity that can reach the seven coordination spheres. (iii)
10 While the presence of methylene groups near the center of WOR triggers the decomposition of complexes,
11 carboxylates may increase the stability of the complex. (iv) Every negative charge in the first coordination
12 sphere decreases redox waves 150-200 mV and this needs to be taken into account for the preparation of
13 WOCs with low overpotential. (v) Flexible ligand backbone may stabilize the WOC in the transition state
14 and decrease activation energy. (vi) The methyl groups on the benzene ring are ready to be oxidized due
15 to low C-H bond-dissociation energy by oxygen atom insertion.

16

17 Table 3. Electronic and structural factors of **10**, **14b**, and **22a** as represent the three main groups of Ru-based
18 complexes in active mode at pH1, the factors are collected from activate catalysts.

Group	Ru(N) ₆	Ru(N) ₅ (O)	Ru(N) ₄ (O) ₂
Catalyst	10	14b	22a
Negative Charge	2	1	2
Bite angle	~101	180	124
Overpotential	~230	~380	~200

19

20

1 **5- Lesson learned from RWOCs to the other WOCs**

2 To imply the lesson learned from RWOC to the other metal-based WOCs, Lau *et al.* reported a cobalt
3 complex with qpy equatorial ligand called $[\text{Co}(\text{qpy})(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ (**33**), and the activity was compared with
4 $[\text{Co}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ (Figure 19 a). The qpy ligand showed higher stability than bpy (335 vs 206).[117]
5 Based on the lesson learned from RWOC, and taking into consideration the reported stability of the
6 complex, we suggest adding one negative charge to the qpy equatorial ligand to decrease overpotential
7 by around 150 mV and increase the stability of the metal center at a high oxidation state. This negative
8 charge can be introduced by replacing one of py ligands with a carboxylate group (Figure 19b). To note
9 here, some of the ligands which provide a negative charge to the metal center can have dual effects in the
10 WOR. For instance, in phosphate groups, one oxygen that is coordinated to the metal center decreases
11 overpotential and the second one can act as the proton acceptor from the aqua ligand. Significantly, the
12 presence of auxiliary ligands near to the metal center, which can remove a proton from incoming water,
13 can also decrease overpotential, [114, 118-120] however; our personal experience suggests, the positive
14 effect of these auxiliary ligands for designing new WOC is challenging. Since the too-close auxiliary
15 ligands can block the metal center and deactivate the complex or decrease the activity [61,97,121] while
16 auxiliary ligands that are too far can have a negative effect.[122] Marelius *et al.* reported that the presence
17 of auxiliary hydroxy groups in the $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_5(\text{O})$ family of complexes leads to the inactive WOC for unclear
18 reasons.[120] On the other hand, some auxiliary ligands showed activity with electrochemical oxidation,
19 while they are still inactive in the presence of Ce^{IV} as the chemical oxidant.[104] Another way to decrease
20 the overpotential is by placing EDGs on aromatic rings in the first coordination sphere. Nevertheless,
21 doing so decreases the stability of WOCs[123], and based on electrochemical experiments their effects
22 on high oxidation state Ru-bda complexes are not confirmed. To our knowledge, the direct coordination
23 of negative ligands to the metal center, discussed here, ensures the decreasing overpotential and stability
24 enhancement.

Figure 19. a) The octahedral Co complex (**33**) reported to be stable during water oxidation and b) converting N_4 quaterdentate equatorial ligand to N_3O and reducing overpotential by placing a negative charge to the first coordination sphere. Fig. 19a, adapted from Ref. [117].

1 In this part, we will discuss pathways to increase the stability of the ligand backbone. Lloret *et al.* reported
 2 a series of molecular Fe complexes in which the complexes with labile sites in the cis configuration were
 3 active (Figure 20a).[124] However, recent research suggests that after adding an oxidant, decomposition
 4 occurs.[125, 126] Such type of decomposition is also reported in other molecular complexes which are
 5 reinvestigated [126, 127] or they have been reported for the first time with different types of a molecular
 6 catalyst such as Ni [128, 129], Mn [130], and Co [128, 131]. The investigation of different Ru based
 7 WOCs [97, 98] together with the similar structures of WOCs which are stable[116, 132, 133] versus
 8 unstable[39, 99, 128] ones, guide us that the most possible source of CO_2 release during O_2 gas detection
 9 comes from the oxidation of methylene groups in ligand backbone.[127, 134] Arguably, we suggest a
 10 rational modification by replacing hydrogen atoms in the methylene groups in the ligand backbone with
 11 methyl groups (Figure 20b). It is worth mentioning that such modification will be useful to increase the
 12 stability if the ligand is coordinated strongly to the metal center. Else, after dissolving the complex, the
 13 ligand will release the metal center in the solution and any modification on the ligand backbone will not
 14 alter the stability.[125]

Figure 20. a) Fe complex (**34a**) which is reinvestigated and its decomposition has been suggested, Red circles are the positions prone to be the starting point of decomposition in the ligand backbone, and b) hydrogen atoms on methylene groups in complex **34a** are assigned with green color to target stability increase in **34b**. Molecular structure of Fig. 20a adapted from ref. [124].

1 To investigate a series of ligands that are not reported or are commercially available to facilitate the
 2 rational design of ligand backbone in WOC, pyrrole is one of the aromatic compounds that can be probed
 3 instead of pyridine to provide a negative charge to the metal centers. Moreover, we have chosen pyrrole
 4 ligand backbones as they are flexible to adjust themselves in transition states. If ligand a in Figure 21 is
 5 selected to synthesize the MWOC, based on RWOCs lesson learned, the first concern will be the oxidation
 6 of methyl alcohol ligands during water oxidation which triggers the decomposition of the catalyst. In the
 7 case of ligand b, this issue has been resolved, however; positions 3,3' and 4,4' in 2,2'-bipyrrole are ready
 8 to start polymerization in acidic and basic conditions. Arguably, we will move to ligand c, in which the
 9 methyl groups blocked positions 3,3' and 4,4'. Nevertheless, in this review, we showed one of the
 10 decomposition pathways for Ru(bda) complexes is related to the oxidation of the benzylic group on the
 11 axial pyridine ligands which have low C-H Bond-dissociation energy. Convincingly, we will suggest
 12 ligand d as the robust ligand backbone in which *t*-Bu decreases the chance of oxidation instead of methyl
 13 groups.

Figure 21. Ligand backbones are chosen to implement the strategic factors discussed for designing the next generation of MWOCs. The points which are prone to oxidation and trigger decompositions are assigned by red color which in the case of a) 3 points, b) 2 points, c) 1 point, and d) Zero have been assigned. For simplicity, the symmetric positions of the decomposition points are not assigned. To design a new group of WOCs, $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_3(\text{O})_3$, one pyrrole can be replaced with pyridine in a – d ligands.

1

2 6- Conclusion and Perspective for designing next Generation of RWOCs ($\text{Ru}(\text{N})_4(\text{O})_3$)

3 The discovery of blue dimer was a starting point for gigantic progress in the field of molecular water
 4 oxidation catalysis that resulted in the introduction of different RWOCs with high rates and stability
 5 together with the exploration of two new mechanisms of water oxidation reaction called WNA and I2M.

6 We have classified the water oxidation catalysis complexes into three main groups, including $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_6$,
 7 $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_5(\text{O})$, and $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_4(\text{O})_2$. The experimental result showed that before water oxidation, the first and
 8 second groups of Ru complexes convert to new active species, which includes oxygen atom transfer to
 9 pyridines in the equatorial ligand of the complex. However, the last group of Ru complexes showed
 10 catalytic activity without showing any change in their structures. The complexes in the last group
 11 ($\text{Ru}(\text{N})_4(\text{O})_2$) are the most robust and active as compared with the other two groups. In the Ru-bda types
 12 of complex, owing to the wide bite angle and the presence of two carboxylic groups which stabilize the
 13 metal center at a higher oxidation state, WOR evolves at a high rate, stability, and relatively low
 14 overpotential. Although, the $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_4(\text{O})_2$ family of complexes has opened a new pathway for the research
 15 community to rationally design WOCs with high stability and activity; it has still around 200 mV
 16 overpotentials. As the ligands with negative charge coordinated to Ru center decrease the oxidation
 17 potential, a new family of WOCs with a general formula $\text{Ru}(\text{N})_3(\text{O})_3$ and wide bite angle, can be the next-

1 generation WOCs with low overpotential”, that can make it more efficient. The discussed factors applied
2 to the other WOCs for designing next-generation catalysts.

3 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

4 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests that could have appeared to
5 influence the work reported in this paper.

6 **Acknowledgments**

7 We gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by Basque regional ELARTEK project
8 ENSOL2. This work received funding from the European Union H2020 Programme under a European
9 Research Council Consolidator grant [MOLEMAT, 726360].

10 **Keywords:** Water oxidation; artificial photosynthesis; global warming; molecular catalysis; sustainable
11 energy

12

13 **References**

- 14 [1] J. Su, L. Vayssieres, *ACS Energy Lett.* 1 (2016) 121-135.
15 [2] M. Muller, *Nature* 566 (2019) 315-317.
16 [3] S.L. Lewis, C.E. Wheeler, E.T. Mitchard, A. Koch, *Nature* 568 (2019) 25-28.
17 [4] A. Grubler, C. Wilson, N. Bento, B. Boza-Kiss, V. Krey, D.L. McCollum, N.D. Rao, K. Riahi, J. Rogelj, S. De
18 Stercke, *Nat. Energy* 3 (2018) 515-527.
19 [5] D.L. McCollum, W. Zhou, C. Bertram, H.-S. De Boer, V. Bosetti, S. Busch, J. Després, L. Drouet, J. Emmerling,
20 M. Fay, *Nat. Energy* 3 (2018) 589-599.
21 [6] S. Roe, C. Streck, M. Obersteiner, S. Frank, B. Griscom, L. Drouet, O. Fricko, M. Gusti, N. Harris, T. Hasegawa,
22 Z. Hausfather, P. Havlík, J. House, G.-J. Nabuurs, A. Popp, M.J.S. Sánchez, J. Sanderman, P. Smith, E. Stehfest, D.
23 Lawrence, *Nat. Clim. Change.* 9 (2019) 817-828.
24 [7] C.L. Fyson, S. Baur, M. Gidden, C.-F. Schleussner, *Nat. Clim. Change.* 10 (2020) 836-841.
25 [8] D.P. Van Vuuren, E. Stehfest, D.E. Gernaat, M. Van Den Berg, D.L. Bijl, H.S. De Boer, V. Daioglou, J.C.
26 Doelman, O.Y. Edelenbosch, M. Harmsen, *Nat. Clim. Change.* 8 (2018) 391-397.
27 [9] G. Realmonde, L. Drouet, A. Gambhir, J. Glynn, A. Hawkes, A.C. Köberle, M. Tavoni, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019)
28 1-12.
29 [10] R.S. Middleton, J.D. Oglan-Hand, B. Chen, J.M. Bielicki, K.M. Ellett, D.R. Harp, R.M. Kammer, *Energy*
30 *Environ. Sci.* 13 (2020) 5000-5016.,
31 [11] O. Boucher, V. Bellassen, H. Benveniste, P. Ciais, P. Criqui, C. Guivarch, H. Le Treut, S. Mathy, R. Sférian,
32 *PNAS* 113 (2016) 7287-7290.
33 [12] J. Rogelj, A. Popp, K.V. Calvin, G. Luderer, J. Emmerling, D. Gernaat, S. Fujimori, J. Strefler, T. Hasegawa, G.
34 Marangoni, *Nat. Clim. Change.* 8 (2018) 325.
35 [13] F. Creutzig, P. Agoston, J.C. Goldschmidt, G. Luderer, G. Nemet, R.C. Pietzcker, *Nat. Energy* 2 (2017) 17140.

- 1 [14] S.C. Peter, *ACS Energy Lett.* 3 (2018) 1557-1561.
- 2 [15] W.A. Braff, J.M. Mueller, J.E. Trancik, *Nat. Clim. Change.* 6 (2016) 964-969.
- 3 [16] G.F. Nemet, *How solar energy became cheap: A model for low-carbon innovation*, Routledge 2019.
- 4 [17] N. Kannan, D. Vakeesan, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 62 (2016) 1092-1105.
- 5 [18] J.D. Blakemore, R.H. Crabtree, G.W. Brudvig, *Chem. Rev.* 115 (2015) 12974-13005.
- 6 [19] Y. Tachibana, L. Vayssieres, J.R. Durrant, *Nat. Photonics* 6 (2012) 511.
- 7 [20] T.A. Faunce, W. Lubitz, A.B. Rutherford, D. MacFarlane, G.F. Moore, P. Yang, D.G. Nocera, T.A. Moore, D.H. Gregory, S. Fukuzumi, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 6 (2013) 695-698.
- 8 [21] S. Chu, Y. Cui, N. Liu, *Nat. Mater.* 16 (2017) 16-22.
- 9 [22] T. Faunce, S. Styring, M.R. Wasielewski, G.W. Brudvig, A.W. Rutherford, J. Messinger, A.F. Lee, C.L. Hill, H. Degroot, M. Fontecave, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 6 (2013) 1074-1076.
- 10 [23] M. Kondo, H. Tatewaki, S. Masaoka, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 50 (2021) 6790-6831.
- 11 [24] J.-W. Wang, D.-C. Zhong, T.-B. Lu, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 377 (2018) 225-236.
- 12 [25] L.-M. Cao, D. Lu, D.-C. Zhong, T.-B. Lu, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 407 (2020) 213156.
- 13 [26] D.-C. Liu, D.-C. Zhong, T.-B. Lu, *EnergyChem* 2 (2020) 100034.
- 14 [27] L.-M. Cao, J.-W. Wang, D.-C. Zhong, T.-B. Lu, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 6 (2018) 3224-3230.
- 15 [28] D.-C. Liu, L.-M. Cao, Z.-M. Luo, D.-C. Zhong, J.-B. Tan, T.-B. Lu, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 6 (2018) 24920-24927.
- 16 [29] W. Lubitz, M. Chrysin, N. Cox, *Photosyn. Res.* 142 (2019) 105-125.
- 17 [30] W. Zhang, W. Lai, R. Cao, *Chem. Rev.* 117 (2017) 3717-3797.
- 18 [31] Y. Liu, Y. Han, Z. Zhang, W. Zhang, W. Lai, Y. Wang, R. Cao, *Chem. Sci.* 10 (2019) 2613-2622.
- 19 [32] J. Li, C.A. Triana, W. Wan, D.P. Adiyeri Saseendran, Y. Zhao, S.E. Balaghi, S. Heidari, G.R. Patzke, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 50 (2021) 2444-2485.
- 20 [33] K.N. Ferreira, T.M. Iverson, K. Maghlaoui, J. Barber, S. Iwata, *Science* 303 (2004) 1831-1838.
- 21 [34] Y. Umena, K. Kawakami, J.-R. Shen, N. Kamiya, *Nature* 473 (2011) 55.
- 22 [35] M.M. Najafpour, T. Ehrenberg, M. Wiechen, P. Kurz, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 49 (2010) 2233-2237.
- 23 [36] X.-P. Zhang, A. Chandra, Y.-M. Lee, R. Cao, K. Ray, W. Nam, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 50 (2021) 4804-4811.
- 24 [37] F. Liang, P. Lindberg, P. Lindblad, *Sustain. Energy Fuels* 2 (2018) 2583-2600.
- 25 [38] S.W. Gersten, G.J. Samuels, T.J. Meyer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 104 (1982) 4029-4030.
- 26 [39] B.-L. Lee, M.D. Kärkäs, E.V. Johnston, A.K. Inge, L.-H. Tran, Y. Xu, Ö. Hansson, X. Zou, B. Åkermark, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 2010 (2010) 5462-5470.
- 27 [40] J.A. Gilbert, D.S. Eggleston, W.R. Murphy Jr, D.A. Geselowitz, S.W. Gersten, D.J. Hodgson, T.J. Meyer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 107 (1985) 3855-3864.
- 28 [41] D. Moonshiram, V. Purohit, J.J. Concepcion, T.J. Meyer, Y. Pushkar, *Materials* 6 (2013) 392-409.
- 29 [42] F. Liu, J.J. Concepcion, J.W. Jurss, T. Cardolaccia, J.L. Templeton, T.J. Meyer, *Inorg. Chem.* 47 (2008) 1727-1752.
- 30 [43] T.A. Matias, F.N. Rein, R.C. Rocha, A.L.B. Formiga, H.E. Toma, K. Araki, *Dalton Trans.* 48 (2019) 3009-3017.
- 31 [44] C. Sens, I. Romero, M. Rodríguez, A. Llobet, T. Parella, J. Benet-Buchholz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 126 (2004) 7798-7799.
- 32 [45] R. Zong, R.P. Thummel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (2005) 12802-12803.
- 33 [46] J.J. Concepcion, J.W. Jurss, J.L. Templeton, T.J. Meyer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 130 (2008) 16462-16463.
- 34 [47] G. Zhang, R. Zong, H.-W. Tseng, R.P. Thummel, *Inorg. Chem.* 47 (2008) 990-998.
- 35 [48] B. Durham, S.R. Wilson, D.J. Hodgson, T.J. Meyer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 102 (1980) 600-607.
- 36 [49] L. Tong, R. Zong, R. Zhou, N. Kaveevivitchai, G. Zhang, R.P. Thummel, *Faraday Discuss.* 185 (2015) 87-104.
- 37 [50] R. Zong, R.P. Thummel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 126 (2004) 10800-10801.
- 38 [51] D. Moonshiram, Y. Pineda-Galvan, D. Erdman, M. Palenik, R. Zong, R. Thummel, Y. Pushkar, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 138 (2016) 15605-15616.
- 39 [52] A. Ghaderian, A. Franke, M. Gil-Sepulcre, J. Benet-Buchholz, A. Llobet, I. Ivanović-Burmazović, C. Gimbert-Suriñach, *Dalton Trans.* 49 (2020) 17375-17387.
- 40 [53] Z. Liang, R. Zhao, T. Qiu, R. Zou, Q. Xu, *EnergyChem* 1 (2019) 100001.
- 41 [54] Y. Pineda-Galvan, A.K. Ravari, S. Shmakov, L. Lifshits, N. Kaveevivitchai, R. Thummel, Y. Pushkar, *J. Catal.* 375 (2019) 1-7.
- 42 [55] Y. Liu, S.-M. Ng, S.-M. Yiu, W.W.Y. Lam, X.-G. Wei, K.-C. Lau, T.-C. Lau, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 126 (2014) 14696-14699.
- 43 [56] H.-W. Tseng, R. Zong, J.T. Muckerman, R. Thummel, *Inorg. Chem.* 47 (2008) 11763-11773.

- 1 [57] J.L. Boyer, D.E. Polyansky, D.J. Szalda, R. Zong, R.P. Thummel, E. Fujita, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 50 (2011)
2 12600-12604.
- 3 [58] H. Yamazaki, T. Hakamata, M. Komi, M. Yagi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (2011) 8846-8849.
- 4 [59] M. Hirahara, M.Z. Ertem, M. Komi, H. Yamazaki, C.J. Cramer, M. Yagi, *Inorg. Chem.* 52 (2013) 6354-6364.
- 5 [60] S.K. Padhi, R. Fukuda, M. Ehara, K. Tanaka, *Inorg. Chem.* 51 (2012) 5386-5392.
- 6 [61] S. Maji, I. López, F. Bozoglian, J. Benet-Buchholz, A. Llobet, *Inorg. Chem.* 52 (2013) 3591-3593.
- 7 [62] N. Kaveevivitchai, L. Kohler, R. Zong, M. El Ojaimi, N. Mehta, R.P. Thummel, *Inorg. Chem.* 52 (2013) 10615-
8 10622.
- 9 [63] D.J. Wasylenko, C. Ganesamoorthy, B.D. Koivisto, M.A. Henderson, C.P. Berlinguette, *Inorg. Chem.* 49
10 (2010) 2202-2209.
- 11 [64] M. Yagi, S. Tajima, M. Komi, H. Yamazaki, *Dalton Trans.* 40 (2011) 3802-3804.
- 12 [65] S. Watabe, Y. Tanahashi, M. Hirahara, H. Yamazaki, K. Takahashi, E.A. Mohamed, Y. Tsubonouchi, Z.N.
13 Zahran, K. Saito, T. Yui, M. Yagi, *Inorg. Chem.* 58 (2019) 12716-12723.
- 14 [66] S. Masaoka, K. Sakai, *Chem. Lett.* 38 (2009) 182-183.
- 15 [67] T.A. Matias, A.P. Mangoni, S.H. Toma, F.N. Rein, R.C. Rocha, H.E. Toma, K. Araki, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 2016
16 (2016) 5547-5556.
- 17 [68] I. López, M.Z. Ertem, S. Maji, J. Benet-Buchholz, A. Keidel, U. Kuhlmann, P. Hildebrandt, C.J. Cramer, V.S.
18 Batista, A. Llobet, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 53 (2014) 205-209.
- 19 [69] M. Yoshida, M. Kondo, S. Torii, K. Sakai, S. Masaoka, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 54 (2015) 7981-7984.
- 20 [70] B. Zhang, S. Zhan, T. Liu, L. Wang, A. Ken Inge, L. Duan, B.J.J. Timmer, O. Kravchenko, F. Li, M.S.G. Ahlquist,
21 L. Sun, *J. Energy Chem.* 54 (2021) 815-821.
- 22 [71] J. Nyhlén, L. Duan, B. Åkermark, L. Sun, T. Privalov, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 49 (2010) 1773-1777.
- 23 [72] X.-P. Zhang, H.-Y. Wang, H. Zheng, W. Zhang, R. Cao, *Chinese J. Catal.* 42 (2021) 1253-1268.
- 24 [73] J.A. Luque-Urrutia, M. Solà, A. Poater, *Catal. Today* 358 (2020) 278-283.
- 25 [74] L. Duan, L. Wang, A.K. Inge, A. Fischer, X. Zou, L. Sun, *Inorg. Chem.* 52 (2013) 7844-7852.
- 26 [75] L. Duan, F. Bozoglian, S. Mandal, B. Stewart, T. Privalov, A. Llobet, L. Sun, *Nat. Chem.* 4 (2012) 418-423.
- 27 [76] L. Duan, C.M. Araujo, M.S.G. Ahlquist, L. Sun, *PNAS* 109 (2012) 15584-15588.
- 28 [77] S. Zhan, D. Mårtensson, M. Purg, S.C.L. Kamerlin, M.S.G. Ahlquist, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 56 (2017) 6962-
29 6965.
- 30 [78] Y. Xie, D.W. Shaffer, J.J. Concepcion, *Inorg. Chem.* 57 (2018) 10533-10542.
- 31 [79] C.J. Richmond, R. Matheu, A. Poater, L. Falivene, J. Benet-Buchholz, X. Sala, L. Cavallo, A. Llobet, *Chem. Eur.*
32 *J.* 20 (2014) 17282-17286.
- 33 [80] L. Wang, L. Duan, Y. Wang, M.S.G. Ahlquist, L. Sun, *Chem. Commun.* 50 (2014) 12947-12950.
- 34 [81] B. Li, F. Li, S. Bai, Z. Wang, L. Sun, Q. Yang, C. Li, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 8229-8233.
- 35 [82] F. Yu, D. Poole III, S. Mathew, N. Yan, J. Hessels, N. Orth, I. Ivanović-Burmazović, J.N.H. Reek, *Angew. Chem.*
36 *Int. Ed.* 57 (2018) 11247-11251.
- 37 [83] R. Matheu, L. Francàs, P. Chernev, M.Z. Ertem, V. Batista, M. Haumann, X. Sala, A. Llobet, *ACS Catal.* 5
38 (2015) 3422-3429.
- 39 [84] Y. Jiang, F. Li, B. Zhang, X. Li, X. Wang, F. Huang, L. Sun, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 52 (2013) 3398-3401.
- 40 [85] Z. Liu, Y. Gao, M. Zhang, J. Liu, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* 55 (2015) 56-59.
- 41 [86] N. Noll, F. Würthner, *Chem. Eur. J.* 27 (2021) 444-450.
- 42 [87] M. Schulze, V. Kunz, P.D. Frischmann, F. Würthner, *Nat. Chem.* 8 (2016) 576.
- 43 [88] V. Kunz, J.O. Lindner, M. Schulze, M.I.S. Röhr, D. Schmidt, R. Mitrić, F. Würthner, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 10
44 (2017) 2137-2153.
- 45 [89] V. Kunz, M. Schulze, D. Schmidt, F. Würthner, *ACS Energy Lett.* 2 (2017) 288-293.
- 46 [90] S. Zhang, H. Ye, J. Hua, H. Tian, *EnergyChem* 1 (2019) 100015.
- 47 [91] A.-L. Meza-Chincha, J.O. Lindner, D. Schindler, D. Schmidt, A.-M. Krause, M.I.S. Röhr, R. Mitrić, F. Würthner,
48 *Chem. Commun.* 11 (2020) 7654-7664.
- 49 [92] L. Xie, X. Li, B. Wang, J. Meng, H. Lei, W. Zhang, R. Cao, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 58 (2019) 18883-18887.
- 50 [93] F. Li, B. Zhang, X. Li, Y. Jiang, L. Chen, Y. Li, L. Sun, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 50 (2011) 12276-12279.
- 51 [94] L. Xie, X.-P. Zhang, B. Zhao, P. Li, J. Qi, X. Guo, B. Wang, H. Lei, W. Zhang, U.-P. Apfel, R. Cao, *Angew. Chem.*
52 *Int. Ed.* 60 (2021) 7576-7581.
- 53 [95] R. Brimblecombe, G.C. Dismukes, G.F. Swiegers, L. Spiccia, *Dalton Trans.* (2009) 9374-9384.

- 1 [96] D. Schindler, M. Gil-Sepulcre, J.O. Lindner, V. Stepanenko, D. Moonshiram, A. Llobet, F. Würthner, *Adv.*
2 *Energy Mater.* 10 (2020) 2002329.
- 3 [97] A. Ghaderian, J. Holub, J. Benet-Buchholz, A. Llobet, C. Gimbert-Suriñach, *Inorg. Chem.*, 59 (2020) 4443–
4 4452.
- 5 [98] L. Francàs, X. Sala, E. Escudero-Adán, J. Benet-Buchholz, L. Escriche, A. Llobet, *Inorg. Chem.* 50 (2011) 2771–
6 2781.
- 7 [99] J. Yang, B. Liu, L. Duan, *Dalton Trans.* 49 (2020) 4369-4375.
- 8 [100] L. Tong, L. Duan, Y. Xu, T. Privalov, L. Sun, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 50 (2011) 445-449.
- 9 [101] S. Zhan, B. Zhang, L. Sun, M.S.G. Ahlquist, *ACS Catal.* 10 (2020) 13364-13370.
- 10 [102] L. Duan, Y. Xu, P. Zhang, M. Wang, L. Sun, *Inorg. Chem.* 49 (2009) 209-215.
- 11 [103] Y. Liu, G. Chen, S.-M. Yiu, C.-Y. Wong, T.-C. Lau, *ChemCatChem* 10 (2018) 501-504.
- 12 [104] R. Matheu, M.Z. Ertem, J. Benet-Buchholz, E. Coronado, V.S. Batista, X. Sala, A. Llobet, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*
13 137 (2015) 10786-10795.
- 14 [105] J. Creus, R. Matheu, I. Peñafiel, D. Moonshiram, P. Blondeau, J. Benet-Buchholz, J. García-Antón, X. Sala, C.
15 Godard, A. Llobet *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 55 (2016) 15382-15386.
- 16 [106] M.A. Hoque, M. Gil-Sepulcre, A. de Aguirre, J.A.A.W. Elemans, D. Moonshiram, R. Matheu, Y. Shi, J. Benet-
17 Buchholz, X. Sala, M. Malfois, E. Solano, J. Lim, A. Garzón-Manjón, C. Scheu, M. Lanza, F. Maseras, C. Gimbert-
18 Suriñach, A. Llobet, *Nat. Chem.* 12 (2020) 1060-1066.
- 19 [107] M. Ventosa, J. Oliveras, N.G. Bastús, C. Gimbert-Suriñach, V. Puntès, A. Llobet, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 3
20 (2020) 10008-10014.
- 21 [108] A. Shatskiy, A.A. Bardin, M. Oschmann, R. Matheu, J. Benet-Buchholz, L. Eriksson, M.D. Kärkäs, E.V.
22 Johnston, C. Gimbert-Suriñach, A. Llobet, B. Åkermark, *ChemSusChem* 12 (2019) 2251-2262.
- 23 [109] N. Song, J.J. Concepcion, R.A. Binstead, J.A. Rudd, A.K. Vannucci, C.J. Dares, M.K. Coggins, T.J. Meyer, *PNAS*
24 112 (2015) 4935-4940.
- 25 [110] R. Guo, X. Lai, J. Huang, X. Du, Y. Yan, Y. Sun, G. Zou, J. Xiong, *ChemElectroChem* 5 (2018) 3822-3834.
- 26 [111] Y. Xie, D.W. Shaffer, A. Lewandowska-Andralojc, D.J. Szalda, J.J. Concepcion, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 55
27 (2016) 8067-8071.
- 28 [112] J.M. Kamdar, D.C. Marelius, C.E. Moore, A.L. Rheingold, D.K. Smith, D.B. Grotjahn, *ChemCatChem* 8 (2016)
29 3045-3049.
- 30 [113] J.A. Luque-Urrutia, J.M. Kamdar, D.B. Grotjahn, M. Solà, A. Poater, *Dalton Trans.* 49 (2020) 14052-14060.
- 31 [114] D.W. Shaffer, Y. Xie, D.J. Szalda, J.J. Concepcion, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 139 (2017) 15347-15355.
- 32 [115] N. Vereshchuk, R. Matheu, J. Benet-Buchholz, M. Pipelier, J. Lebreton, D. Dubreuil, A. Tessier, C. Gimbert-
33 Suriñach, M.Z. Ertem, A. Llobet, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142 (2020) 5068-5077.
- 34 [116] J. Yang, L. Wang, S. Zhan, H. Zou, H. Chen, M.S.G. Ahlquist, L. Duan, L. Sun, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 373.
- 35 [117] C.-F. Leung, S.-M. Ng, C.-C. Ko, W.-L. Man, J. Wu, L. Chen, T.-C. Lau, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 7903-
36 7907.
- 37 [118] T. Zhang, C. Wang, S. Liu, J.-L. Wang, W. Lin, , *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 136 (2014) 273-281.
- 38 [119] D.K. Dogutan, R. McGuire, D.G. Nocera, , *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (2011) 9178-9180.
- 39 [120] D.C. Marelius, S. Bhagan, D.J. Charboneau, K.M. Schroeder, J.M. Kamdar, A.R. McGettigan, B.J. Freeman,
40 C.E. Moore, A.L. Rheingold, A.L. Cooksy, D.K. Smith, J.J. Paul, E.T. Papish, D.B. Grotjahn, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 2014
41 (2014) 676-689.
- 42 [121] F. Chen, N. Wang, H. Lei, D. Guo, H. Liu, Z. Zhang, W. Zhang, W. Lai, R. Cao, *Inorg. Chem.* 56 (2017) 13368-
43 13375.
- 44 [122] P. Wrzolek, S. Wahl, M. Schwalbe, *Catal. Today* 290 (2017) 28-32.
- 45 [123] A. de Aguirre, P. Garrido-Barros, I. Funes-Ardoiz, F. Maseras, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 2019 (2019) 2109-2114.
- 46 [124] J.L. Fillol, Z. Codolà, I. Garcia-Bosch, L. Gómez, J.J. Pla, M. Costas, *Nature Chemistry*, 3 (2011) 807-813.
- 47 [125] G. Chen, L. Chen, S.-M. Ng, W.-L. Man, T.-C. Lau, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 52 (2013)
48 1789-1791.
- 49 [126] D. Hong, S. Mandal, Y. Yamada, Y.-M. Lee, W. Nam, A. Llobet, S. Fukuzumi, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 52 (2013)
50 9522-9531.
- 51 [127] J.-W. Wang, P. Sahoo, T.-B. Lu, *ACS Catalysis*, 6 (2016) 5062-5068.
- 52 [128] G. Chen, L. Chen, S.-M. Ng, T.-C. Lau, *ChemSusChem*, 7 (2014) 127-134.
- 53 [129] J.-W. Wang, W.-J. Liu, D.-C. Zhong, T.-B. Lu, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 378 (2019) 237-261.
- 54 [130] C.R.R. Gan, Z. Liu, S.-Q. Bai, K.S. Ong, T.S.A. Hor, *Dalton Transactions*, 43 (2014) 1821-1828.

1 [131] S. Fu, Y. Liu, Y. Ding, X. Du, F. Song, R. Xiang, B. Ma, *Chemical Communications*, 50 (2014) 2167-2169.
2 [132] M. Zhang, M.-T. Zhang, C. Hou, Z.-F. Ke, T.-B. Lu, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 53 (2014)
3 13042-13048.
4 [133] M. Gil-Sepulcre, M. Böhler, M. Schilling, F. Bozoglian, C. Bachmann, D. Scherrer, T. Fox, B. Spingler, C.
5 Gimbert-Suriñach, R. Alberto, R. Bofill, X. Sala, S. Lubet, C.J. Richmond, A. Llobet, *ChemSusChem*, 10 (2017)
6 4517-4525.
7 [134] D. Hong, J. Jung, J. Park, Y. Yamada, T. Suenobu, Y.-M. Lee, W. Nam, S. Fukuzumi, *Energy & Environmental*
8 *Science*, 5 (2012) 7606-7616.

9

10

11

12

13

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

25

26

27

28

29

30

31

32

33

34

35

1 Graphical Abstract

2

3

4

5